

ISSN -----

SXC Journal of Management and Social Sciences (SJMSS)

SJMSS

Volume I, Issue I, 2021

SXC Journal of Management and Social Sciences (SJMSS)

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Editorial

I am pleased to announce the first peer-reviewed online publication of St. Xavier's College, SXC Journal of Management and Social Sciences (SJMSS). The SXC Journal of Management and Social Sciences (SJMSS) is an online journal initiated to facilitate research culture among faculties and students from St. Xavier's College. However, SJMSS is not limited to St. Xavier's College researchers alone. We also invite researchers from all over the country and abroad to submit their research papers.

In this Volume 1, Issue 1, 2021, the published articles cover perspective from management, social sciences, and education. I wish to thank the authors who contributed their valuable work to the SJMSS. Importantly, I thank the reviewers who took their time and effort regardless of their busy work schedule for reviewing the manuscript.

On a final note, we welcome researchers to submit their manuscript for the forthcoming Volume 2, Issue 1 in 2022.

Fr. Dr. Augustine Thomas, S.J.
Editor-in-Chief
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